

MANAGEMENT CONSULTANCY SERVICES, A SURVIVAL STRATEGY FOR SMALL AND MEDIUM ENTERPRISES (SMEs): THE NIGERIAN EXPERIENCEOgar, Cassius Ayam*¹,
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Bassey, Moses E³^{*1,2}Accountancy/Business Administration/Banking and Finance, Faculty of Management and Social Sciences, Federal University Ndufu-Alike Ikwo, Nigeria³Business Administration, Faculty of Management Sciences, Cross River University of Technology Nigeria**ABSTRACT**

Majority of entrepreneurs generally lack sufficient managerial know-how, they are unaware of standards, processes and approaches in providing quality services. Average owner-managers have only basic formal education which shows the lack of rudimentary management techniques in running sustainable business. The purpose of the study was to explore the managerial opportunities offered by management consultants in fostering growth and sustainability of SMEs. The specific objective was to determine whether there is any significant relationship between management consultancy services and SMEs' growth which formed part of the theoretical assumption in the research. The researcher adopted an exploratory survey design with an interpretivism philosophy using Calabar metropolis of Cross River State, Nigeria as a pilot city for the study. The target population comprised of all owner-managers of SMEs in the region, but the accessible sample size of 80 SMEs was drawn using Taro Yamane formula from a sample population of 100 SMEs in the area. Close-ended questionnaire were designed and administered to the sampled population covering 7 sub-sector of the economy. The Pearson Product Moment Correlation (r) technique and Z-test technique were adopted to ascertain the relationship and significance of the variables in the research. The result statistically revealed a positive correlation of $r=0.39$ and Z-test result of 7.3 implying that management consultancy services are related to SMEs growth and contributes significantly to the sustainability of SMEs in the region. It was concluded that if owner-managers apply management consultancy services (MCS) in their businesses there would be enhance rate of SMEs successes.

Keywords:

Managerial capital, Consultancy Services, Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs)

INTRODUCTION

Large literature in development economics and entrepreneurship aims to understand the impediments to firm growth, particularly for little and medium-sized enterprises. The majority of the concentrate so far has been on money related imperatives as a focal deterrent to firm development. For instance, pragmatic studies have analyzed these challenges at the small scale level (with loaning tests, see the audit article Banerjee, Karlan, and Zinman 2015; with money concede tests, de Mel, McKenzie, and Woodruff 2008; Karlan, Knight, and Udry 2015; McKenzie 2015) and in addition at the macro level (King and Levine 1993; Rajan and Zingales 1998). Be that as it may, capital alone cannot substantiate the total of firm development; "managerial capital" is required to know how to efficiently utilize the capital in an optimal level. Bruhn, Karlan, and Shoar (2010) contended that managerial capital can specifically influence the firm by enhancing key and operational choices, yet can likewise influence the firm by expanding the profitability of different factors, for example, physical capital and human resources, by helping the firm utilize them all the more effectively. The entrance of owner-mangers to consulting and mentoring services enhances their administrative aptitudes which prepares them to expel bottlenecks to their growth and development.

Series of studies, have demonstrated the need for management consultancy services as key features fundamental to the accomplishment of Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs) sustainability (Deakins, 2000). As indicated by Barisic and Bozicevic (2013), a balanced mix of entrepreneurial qualities and connected managerial know-how is pivotal for SMEs competitive advantage. Managerial consulting is basically a process of prompting entrepreneurial owners in taking care of business issues for which they need aptitude, learning and experience. As opined by the International Council of Management Consulting Institutes (ICMCI), managerial consulting is

the supply of autonomous guidance and help about the procedure of management of customers with management obligations.

Working with consultants, business people/administrators instruct themselves and construct or enhance their administrative abilities. Practically speaking, management consulting helps emerging and maturing professional and dynamic SME managers to successfully manage change and specific management operations effectively (Dukić and Milivojević, 2011).

SMEs are known to be extremely fundamental to the improvement national economies, however Small and Medium Enterprises have contributed significantly to the upgrade of real economies of the world (Lukacs, 2005). They are seen as the spines of the Nigerian economy due to their different contributions (Uchegbulam et al. 2015). Analysis by the IFC shows that approx. 96% of Nigerian firms are SMEs but these seems apparently different in comparison with 53% in the US and 65% in Europe. SME contributes about 90% of product from the manufacturing sector of the Nigerian. They contribute approx. 40% of GDP in Asian countries and half in the US or Europe. The 2013 SMEDAN and National Bureau of Statistics Survey reveals that the total number of individuals employed by the SME sector as at December, 2013 stood at 59,741,211, thus addressing 84.02% of the total work drive unemployment challenges. SMEs contribute up to 46.7% of national GDP in Nigeria in real terms (Alochenu, 2014).

Statement of the Problem

Research has demonstrated that there has been a fall in market development associated with SMEs in different sectors in Nigeria because of deficient use of their organizational assets, absence of execution of specific policies, techniques and activities design to enhance market development in firms are suggested to be responsible for the short fall of SMEs in the region (Uchegbulam et al. 2015). Likewise, as properly posited by Spiegel (1994), it an absence of interest in human capital development, not an absence of interest in physical capital alone, which has kept poor nations from meeting-up to speed with rich ones. Instructive fulfillment and open spending on training are related emphatically to monetary development. As indicated by edufrica.com of the 180 million Nigerians, 54 million needs formal training. This constitutes an incredible drawback to owner-managers in Nigeria.

Study and explanation of business competitiveness is a recurrent theme studied by academics, consultants and practitioners. The internalization of economy, dynamic nature of the environment, greater competitive firms, the need for continuous innovation, product customization and growing use of ICT forces firms to face challenges of improving their competitiveness. These difficulties are greater for small and medium enterprises because their economy of scale and their resources are less than those of large firms. Research has documented that 70% of SMEs fail in their first three years of operations in Nigeria (Akingbolu, 2014). This shows that SMEs in Nigeria are struggling to survive talk less of growth. Just like Hussey as sited by Ezine (2010) rightly points out that “small businesses do not fail for lack of money, fierce economic competition or because of the nature of the operating economy. They fail because the owners think they're good at what they do, forgetting that there are others doing exactly the same thing”. The 2013 SMEDAN and National Bureau of Statistics Survey revealed that “most of the entrepreneurs interviewed are not aware of SMEDAN and their services. The beneficiaries of SMEDAN services are very minimal in virtually all the states”.

As indicated by Barisic and Bozicevic, (2013) for SMEs to operate efficiently and effectively, it is important to draw in specialists who can offer them valid business information and opportunities, and pass on to them a significant volume of basic leadership skills. The fact that most business owners are reluctant to delegate important decisions to employed managers is a significant limiting factor in their successful development. Lack of expertise in planning, the lack of time of business owners to devote more seriously to long-term planning, is one of the main reasons for the stagnation and decline of small businesses. SMEs are in most cases formed by experts in a particular industry, which possess perfect knowledge of their profession in the context of technical competence, but they have a lack of knowledge and experience in management. In this way they run their company into trouble because all the attention is focused on strictly professional technical knowledge and skills, and managerial skills are neglected.

Reception of new administrative information, aptitudes and skills is imperative precondition and among key variables for achievement of entrepreneurial endeavors, and for improvement and supportable development of SMEs. An Expert/Resource specialist will help in planning and recommending arrangements in view of his extremely expertise and encounter, persuading customers about the viability of proposed arrangements and, if required, aiding the usage (Polanyi, 1967). Barisic (2004, 2007), proposes that managerial consulting is helpful to SMEs on the grounds that it: Gives access to specific information and industry best practice, encourage the

procedure of progress, gives a fair-minded assessment from outside spectators, learning through the procedure of business counseling. Barisic and Bozicevic, (2013) closes from their review that despite the fact that there is a plenty of assets in regards to business advices, however they are not promptly accessible or considered as helpful. The cause for that is relatively low entrepreneurs' absorption capacity and the ability to apply the delivered professional business advices, so that as the result advices largely cannot be adequately utilized which further highlights the need of management consulting to SMEs.

Objectives of the Study

The objectives of the study are:

1. To determine whether there is any significant relationship between management consulting and SMEs' growth.
2. To find out the effect of management consulting on the growth and survival of SMEs. **Research**

Questions

The research was guided by the following research questions;

1. Does management consulting have any significant relationship with SMEs' growth?
2. Does Management consulting have effect on the growth and survival of SMEs?

Research hypotheses

For the purpose of the study, the researcher formulated the following hypotheses;

H₀₁: There is no relationship between management consultancy services and SMEs growth

H₀₂: Management consultancy services do not contribute significantly to the growth and survival of SMEs.

Review of related literature

The Concept of Management Consultancy

The limits between business consultancy and other "client related" practices, for example, tutoring, coaching or counseling seem indistinct. It will be exhibited at a later point that advisors themselves concur on saying that occasionally their part inside the customer's association is hazy. Kakabadse, Louchart and Kakabadse (2006) contended that business consultancy has been lifted with its own particular petard and that the perplexity towards the part of business experts is really the aftereffect of their own prosperity. As recommended by McLarty and Robinson (1998: 256), the previous decade has seen 'a remarkable extension in administration consultancy', however it is imperative that business consultancy is recognized from "specialist co-ops" rehearses who announce themselves to be experts.

Coaching is regularly acclimatized to consultancy. This idea is characterized by Brown (1990: 18) as a procedure in which 'an accomplished veteran shapes or guides a newcomer'. Different scholastics embrace a somewhat more logical perspective of coaching in accepting that a tutor is somebody 'who enables someone else to end up what the individual yearns for' (Gladstone, 1988: 1). The writing recommends that mentorship is the relationship existing between a tutor and his "protégé" where the previous, by means of sharing his encounters, goes about as a manual for the newcomer in the association. Despite the fact that there are comparable attributes amongst mentorship and business consultancy, the previous includes the possibility of advancement and upward portability that is inadequate in the idea of business consultancy (Appelbaum et al, 1994).

Guiding is another training regularly misconstrued and compared to the procedure of consultancy. Carroll, (1995: 26) affirms that the two practices are distinctive while taking note of that 'instructors are not normally administration specialists, and not more often than not in a solid position to survey the prosperity of an association and its impacts on its representatives'. One could contend that the fundamental differentiator amongst directing and counseling remains in the way that guiding includes a more interpretive instead of systematic approach. Hannabuss (1997) affirms this presumption and brings up the mental measurement supporting the part of advisors; 'guiding embarks to find this internal world and enable the customer to decipher oblivious musings, emotions and pictures' (Hannabuss, 1997: 375). In spite of the fact that, it will be shown later on that business specialists sooner or later do need to receive an intelligent approach, it can't be considered as a center component of their part.

The limit amongst counseling and training additionally seems obscured. In spite of the fact that it can be contended that instructing is in actuality part of the counseling procedure, training includes a more enthusiastic and social approach than counseling, which fundamentally manages breaking down and unraveling complex issues. Lenhardt, (2004: xv) recommends that training goes for 'inducing in every individual an instinctive and social fitness to the improvement of confidence, ontological and social security, the ability to tune in and the ability to assume responsibility of oneself'.

It is for the most part acknowledged that business consultancy initially showed up toward the start of the twentieth century, when Frederic Taylor initially distributed his treatise on Scientific Management in 1911 (Massey, 2003; Pellegrinelli, 2002). Business consultancy because of its various structures is a troublesome procedure to characterize. Notwithstanding, the Institute of Management Consultancy (IMC) endeavored to concede to an "official" meaning of business/administration consultancy. As per this establishment, 'administration consultancy is the administration gave to business, open and alternate endeavors by an autonomous and qualified individual' (IMC referred to in McLarty and Robinson, 1998: 256). Albeit, these definition does not allude to the pretended by business/administration advisors. In another light, the Institute of Consulting characterizes administration consultancy as 'the arrangement to administration of target counsel and help identifying with the procedure, structure, administration and operations of an association in quest for its long haul purposes and destinations. Such help may incorporate the distinguishing proof of alternatives with suggestions; the arrangement of an extra asset; and additionally the usage of arrangements.' Greiner and Metzger's definition (1983: 7) presents us a stage and enables us to obviously comprehend what business consultancy is about. They characterize business consultancy as 'a warning administration contracted for and gave to associations by extraordinarily prepared and qualified people who help, in a target and free way, the customer association to recognize administration issues, examine such issues, prescribe answers for these issues and help when asked for in the usage of arrangements'. In the event that we precisely contemplate Greiner and Metzger's (1983) definition, various focuses merit saying. As indicated by them, business consultancy requires particular aptitudes and a particular level of information so as to enable customers to distinguish the issues experienced.

Types of Management Consultancy

Consultancy practices can be extensively isolated into the accompanying kinds:

Generalist: These are substantial counseling firms that offer an extensive variety of administrations from system counseling and HR to IT and, now and again, outsourcing on a worldwide premise. A significant number of these became out of the review firms, while others created inside IT benefit organizations.

System Consultants: These consultancies are substantially littler than the generalist firms and the greater part of them are American. As the term proposes, they principally offer key exhortation to organizations on an undertaking by-venture premise. This includes long-go arranging, the rearrangement of an organization's structure, legitimization of administrations and items and a general business examination of the organization.

Human Resource Consultants: These are firms offering pro exhortation going from work force arrangement, labor arranging, work improvement, work assessment and modern relations.

Data Technology Consultants: These organizations give pro exhortation going from characterizing data needs, arrangement of programming, frameworks plan, and PC attainability contemplates, executing PC applications and making PC equipment assessments.

Money related Consultants: The expert counsel offered by monetary consultancies ranges from the establishment of budgetary control frameworks, benefit arranging or capital and income planning, office revamping and regulatory courses of action.

Specialty Firms: These are advisors who leave the bigger firms and set up their own consultancy firms in a specific area, offering a master benefit.

The Roles of Management Consulting in Firms

The part of business advisors and the idea of the administrations they offer is mind boggling and vague (Kakabadse, Louchart and Kakabadse, 2006). All through this area, the examination expects to give a response to the inquiry that has induced such a questioning: what is the part of business experts? Kubr et al (2002), distinguished 5 non specific parts of counseling as; accomplishing authoritative purposes and destinations, taking care of administration and business issues, recognizing and seizing new open doors, improving inclining, and executing changes or change operators.

Accomplishing Organizational Purposes and Objectives

All counseling to administration and business tends to seek after a general and abrogating motivation behind helping customers to accomplish their business, social and different objectives. These objectives might be characterized in different ways: sectoral initiative, upper hand, consumer loyalty, accomplishing absolute quality or efficiency, corporate perfection, superior, benefit, enhanced business comes about, viability, development, and so on. It might accept that the proprietor chief has characterized such objectives however this isn't the situation. The specialist causes the proprietor administrator to build up a dream without bounds, set desire

however reasonable objectives, build up a system, concentrate on results, and begin seeing current issues and openings in the light of longer term and more essential authoritative objectives.

Taking care of Organizational Uncertainties and Business Problems

It shows up from the writing that supervisors' vulnerability towards the quick changing condition is a center component of the interest for counseling administrations (Kakabadse, Louchart and Kakabadse, 2006). Assisting directors and other chiefs with critical thinking is presumably the most continuous part of advisors. SMEs are torment with so much issues as: whining customers, poor business comes about, surprising misfortune, cataclysmic event, loss of critical market, absence of point of view, old control framework, wrong speculation decisions, missed open door, high staff turnover, absence of money, sit without moving assets, weight of rivalry, interior clashes, inability to meet targets, and so on.

Recognizing and Seizing New Opportunities

These parts have been perceived by numerous business companies and associations that are all around oversaw and aggressive. They view counseling as a wellspring of important data and thoughts that can be transformed into an extensive variety of activities, advancements and enhancements in any region or capacity of business: growing new markets and items, evaluating and utilizing best in class advances, enhancing quality, ending up more helpful to clients, upgrading the utilization of monetary asset, finding new business contacts (and contracts), and so forth.

Improving Organizational Learning

Turner (1988: 12) takes note of that 'the accentuation of counseling has changed from "taking care of issues" to building customers' ability for diagnosing circumstances all alone and in this way overseeing all the more adequately progressively, administration specialists are justified regardless of their charges not just as a result of their capacity to examine customer issues and give sound suggestions, yet additionally due to their aptitudes in leading a human procedure that encourages required learning and change'. Business experts, when taking a shot at ventures with customers, encourage hierarchical realizing, which gives off an impression of being a center component of associations' survival right now (Kakabadse, Louchart and Kakabadse, 2006). Burnes et al (2003) contend that with the always showing signs of change condition that organizations work in these days, an association would not survive in the event that it neglected to learn in any event as quick as its condition changed.

Usage of Change/Change Agents

It is contended that quicker changes make weaker circumstances and subsequently legitimize a requirement for outside help. In that sense, the advisor's part is more than essentially consoling chiefs and lightening sentiments of vulnerability, it is likewise to encourage authoritative change. As verified by Brown and Eisenhard (1998), the best-performing organizations, through the mastery of the business, set the pace and musicality of progress, and one can contend that the part of experts isn't just to exchange their aptitudes to customers however to enable them to make the switch or catch-to up with it.

McKinley and Scherer (2000) explored the unexpected results of rebuilding in associations. They theorized that there is a connection between the compositions of specialists and authoritative rebuilding. As indicated by them, the compositions of advisors on authoritative change drive top-administrators to rebuild associations, which lead experts to compose significantly more; in this way giving the impression of a perpetual circle.

To close on this area of characterizing the part of business advisors, the equivocal character of the part of business specialists ought to be pushed. It has so far been noticed that specialists assume distinctive parts.

The Definition, Operations and Challenges of Small and Medium Scale Enterprises in Nigeria

The meaning of SMEs has a tendency to change as indicated by the idea of its exercises, the reason for the definition, and the level of advancement where the endeavor is found. The criteria for portraying an endeavor as "little" may be the quantity of workers, the cash estimation of offers, capital venture, greatest vitality prerequisites or different mixes of these and different components. As the ILO proposes, it is up to every nation to detail its own meaning of SMEs. Nonetheless, in many exchanges and works regarding the matter by administration specialists, a little venture is taken as one in which the authoritative and operational administration is in the hands of maybe a couple people (Kubr et al, 2002).

In Nigeria throughout the years there have been discussions in writing concerning fitting meanings of SMEs. Nigeria is as yet attempting to get a bound together definition out of the few conflicting and vague definition proffered by a few ventures and offices, for example, the 1992 audit by the National Council on mechanical Standards that characterized little and medium scale endeavors (SMEs) as undertakings with add up to cost (counting working capital however barring expense of land) above N31m yet not surpassing N3, 150m, with a

work size of in the vicinity of 11 and 100 representatives. The Federal Ministry of Industries characterizes a medium scale undertaking as any organization with working resources under 200 million, and utilizing under 300 people. A little scale undertaking, then again, is one that has add up to resources under 50 million, with under 100 representatives. The National Economic Reconstruction Fund (NERFUND) characterizes a SSE as one whose aggregate resources is under 10 million, yet made no reference either to its yearly turnover or the quantity of workers.

The scientist receives the SMEDAN and NBS definition as the most proper due to their double classification as demonstrated as follows;

Table 1: Definition of SMEs

Size Category	Employment	Assets (₦ Million)
Micro enterprises	Less than 10	Less than 5
Small enterprises	10 to 49	5 to less than 50
Medium enterprises	50 to 199	50 to less than 500

Source: SMEDAN & NBS Survey Report, 2013

In the event that there exists a contention on grouping amongst work and resources criteria (for instance, if a venture has resources worth seven million naira (N7M) however utilizes 7 people), the business based order will come first and the undertaking would be viewed as smaller scale. The benefits reject land and building.

SMEs particularly exhibit a high level of development and adaptability in their business condition (Rae, 2005; Pavlovic, 2009). Dealing with an organization in a circumstance of absence of assets influences the meaning of the authoritative structure of SMEs. SMEs constitutes of few representatives, the workers play out various capacities in the organization, and frequently a proprietor plays out numerous capacities. There is no much specialization in light of the fact that the director or proprietor handles the financing, generation, showcasing and work force of the venture. Administration of any private venture is normally autonomous. The proprietor chief knows and is known by all representatives in the firm and the little scale business is worked like a sole proprietorship. They take part in the creation of light and purchaser arranged products. They have next to zero bookkeeping records. As far as investible store, size of operation and number of individuals utilized, the extent of the business is moderately little.

SMEs in Nigeria keep on facing various issues, for example, precarious large scale financial condition. This outcomes in exorbitant working condition because of high swelling and high import reliance, high obligation trouble on the country, absence of access to innovation and best of breed business arrangements, business benefits, counseling and preparing. Government administration, which builds SMEs working costs, for example, threatening legal process, administrative and business condition. Absence of administrative offices and venture bolster administrations, for example, constrained ability to business relationship, for instance Chambers of Commerce absence of short and long haul capital. Likewise most SMEs business people need administrative money to run and develop their organizations little ponder 70% of SMEs bomb in their initial three years of operations (Akingbolu, 2014).

The Need of Management Consulting In SMES

Bruhn (2011) attests that SMEs in creating nations appear to develop slower than equal firms in the created world. This might be because of absence of administrative capital. There is considerable research supporting the need to oversee information in associations today (Cook and Brown, 1999) and learning is accepted to be profoundly established inside associations (Sturdy et al., 2009; Prokesch, 1995). Truth be told associations can be viewed as a learning life form that always advances through little exercises and different endeavors to catch data remotely and inside, forming it into valuable information inside the organization (Prokesch, 1995).

Nonaka (1994) and Prokesch, (1995) demonstrates that cutting edge organizations, expansive and little, must discover, create and use the inside learning inside organizations to make it accessible to everybody in the organization. This information, which can be unsaid or unequivocal in nature (Nonaka, 1994; Nonaka, Toyama, Kono, 2000; Cook and Yanow, 1993; Örténblad, 2005; Engelhardt and Simmons, 2002), is generally accepted to bring about an upper hand and advantage those that can deal with adapting superior to others (Senge and Sterman, 1992; Dodgson, 1993; Stewart, 2001; Nonaka et al., 2000). Associations today are endeavoring to

adapt to immense and expanding measure of data (Engelhardt and Simmons, 2002) and there is an issue in attempting to transform data into helpful information that can be utilized by the association (Jaenson, 1997).

It should then shock no one that administration advisors have developed in significance being seen as in the cutting edge in bringing new learning into associations; as change operators or promoters of administration styles (Sturdy et al., 2009) and as the model of information serious firms (Werr and Stjernberg, 2003). Consequently, learning can't be withdrawn from specialists as it intercedes the experts rehearse (Sturdy and Wright, 2011) subsequently their pertinence to SMEs for development and survival.

As distinguished by Kubr et al (2005), SMEs are tormented with so much issues as: whining customers, poor business comes about, sudden misfortune, cataclysmic event, loss of essential market, absence of viewpoint, out of date control framework, wrong speculation decisions, missed open door, high staff turnover, absence of money, sit without moving assets, weight of rivalry, inward clashes, inability to meet targets, and so on. To control these issues, Kubr et al (2005) places 10 main ways specialists can render help. Some of them are;

Giving Information: Better, more total and more important data is frequently the primary or just the thing micro business owners need to settle on the correct choices. It might be data on business sectors, clients, segment patterns, crude materials, providers, contenders, potential accomplices, wellsprings of designing mastery, government arrangements and controls, or other.

Giving Specialist Resources: An expert can be utilized to supplement the staffs of SMEs. Normally such advisors will be pro in territories where the proprietor administrator is searching for here and now skill, or needs to abstain from enlisting another representative.

Setting up Business Contacts and Linkages: SMEs experience the ill effects of such a great amount from this. They do not have the contacts/connect in their industry or crosswise over enterprises that can support their operation. Specialists frequently offers new business contacts, operators, delegates, providers, subcontractors, joint-wander accomplices, business and expert systems, wellsprings of financing, extra speculators et cetera.

Giving Expert Opinion: Most proprietor's supervisors do not have the aptitude, experience and know-how to settle on savvy business choices. Experts can offer proficient sentiments and business other options to SMEs in center zones like long haul business arranging, showcasing, monetary bookkeeping, and so on.

Indicative Work: The proprietor supervisor frequently does not have what it takes and knowledge to find where the firm needs consideration. Symptomatic abilities and instruments are among the advisor's vital resources. Experts can perform extensive variety of analytic undertakings concerning the association's qualities and shortcomings, positive and negative patterns, potential for development, boundaries to change, focused position, underutilized assets, specialized or human issues requiring administration's consideration et cetera.

Quantifye.co likewise recognizes 10 reasons why SMEs needs counseling. Some of them are that advisors can help in the arrangement of a hearty business and showcasing plan, give money related mastery expected to business strength, offer the important business abilities required for proficient administration, offer prescribed procedures in business to maintain a strategic distance from assents and loss of altruism, enable present new viewpoint and furthermore to distinguish issues influencing the business on account of their objectivity.

Management Consulting Process Model for SMEs

The model concentrates on counseling issues at different stages and ventures in the advancement of customer advisor affiliations. The model is relied upon to help experts and furthermore the proprietor administrator in doing a successful counseling exercise. It ought to be especially useful where customer association is basic to executing answers for counseling issues.

As indicated by Bruckman and Iman (n.d.), counseling assignments for SMEs can be seen as comprising of six stages. The periods of Contact, Problem Definition, Data Search, Analysis, Plan Development, and Implementation require distinctive exercises and give isolate difficulties to both the customer and specialist. A comprehension of the necessities of each stage is particularly imperative in the general arranging of venture exercises, inside a system of time accessible to the specialist.

So also, Peter Block in his book *Flawless Consulting* recommended a 5 stages way to deal with counseling. Here's an outline of the diverse stages as likewise featured in Fig 3.

Passage and Contracting: This first stage manages the underlying contact with the customer about the undertaking. The underlying contact between a potential customer and the advisor is a basic one; both the customer and specialist must build up desires of responsibility and genius (Bruckman and Iman (n.d.). Assignments include:

1. Setting up the principal meeting.
2. Exploring what the issue is.

3. Determining in case you're the correct specialist for the work.
4. Listing the customer's desires.
5. Specifying what desires you have.
6. Figuring out how to begin.

At the point when specialists discuss their fiascos, their decision is normally that the task was flawed in the underlying contracting stage.

Figure 3: Management Consultancy Process Model

Source: Block, P: Flawless Consulting (2000).

Impact of Management Consultancy Services on the Growth of SMEs

Research has demonstrated that administration consultancy administrations has sensible effect on the development of SMEs (Bruhn, Karlan, and Shoar, 2010; Kubr et al, 2005). Business Growth is the way toward enhancing some measure of an undertaking's prosperity (Business Dictionary, 2017). SMEs must develop on the off chance that it wishes to keep up as a going concern. Hierarchical development can possibly furnish independent companies with a heap of advantages, including things like more noteworthy efficiencies from economies of scale, expanded power, a more prominent capacity to withstand showcase changes, an expanded survival rate, grater benefits, and expanded distinction for firm individuals. Authoritative development be that as it may, implies diverse things to various associations. There are numerous parameters go with may use to gauge its development. Since a definitive objective of most organizations is benefit, most organizations will gauge their development as far as net benefit, income, and other money related information. Other proprietor directors may utilize one of the accompanying criteria for evaluating their development: deals, number of representatives, physical extension, achievement of a product offering, or expanded piece of the pie. At last, achievement and development will be checked by how well a firm does with respect to the objectives it has set for itself (inc.com).

The exploration demonstrated in section three demonstrates the parameters used to show SMEs development. Various existing writing features the beneficial outcomes of counseling on SMEs. In any case, for beneficial

outcomes to be seen, the proprietor supervisor must actualize the specialist's proposals. Likewise, the counseling procedure should keep going for a sensible measure of time say a half year. Bruhn, Karlan, and Shoar (2010), from their examination of 432 SMEs were 150 out of the 432 were arbitrarily gotten the treatment. The staying 282 endeavors filled in as control assembles that did not get any financed counseling administrations. Their examination demonstrated the constructive outcome of counseling administrations on the development of SMEs. They closed along these lines: "We demonstrate that entrance to management consultancy effectively affected aggregate factor efficiency and profit for resources (around 0.2 standard deviations, with respect to the control gathering). Proprietors likewise had huge increment in "entrepreneurial soul" (a file that measures entrepreneurial certainty and objective setting). We additionally locate a relentless huge increment (around half) in the quantity of workers and aggregate wage charge even five years after the program. We record huge heterogeneity in the particular administrative practices that enhanced because of the counseling, however the three most noticeable regions are advertising, money related bookkeeping, and long haul business arranging". The Stanford Social Innovation Review (SSIR), in their resulting assessment of the program led by Bruhn, Karlan, and Shoar (2010) found a 80% expansion in deals and a 120% expansion in benefits for the SMEs who got the counseling administrations. Different impacts are featured in this manner, which are not comprehensive; Add up to Factor Productivity: TFP is the proficiency and viability with which information, for example, structures, apparatus, and work are mutually utilized for the yield of merchandise and enterprises. Bruhn (2011) brings up that the offering of consultancy administrations can prompt higher efficiency with a similar measure of contributions (for instance, by keeping up apparatus or better promoting or estimating procedures). Enhance Managerial Decisions: Managerial capital because of consultancy administrations can enhance choices on the sum and sort of information sources a firm purchases or leases. Likewise it can enhance the manner by which SMEs utilize their funds along these lines expanding their entrance to back. Increment Sales: Consultancy services offers SMEs distinctive showcasing methodologies to achieve their business sectors differentiate and enter new markets.

Theoretical Framework

Werr and Styhre (2003) separate the writing on management consulting into two methodologies: the functionalist viewpoint and the critical point of view. The basic viewpoint, which happened amid the 1990s as management consulting expanded in fame (Mohe and Seidl, 2011), censures the utilitarian way to deal with management consulting. Here, the specialist is seen as the commanding party in the relationship (Werr and Styhre, 2003). These two viewpoints shape the hypothetical system as talked about beneath.

The Functionalist Theory

The functionalist point of view is a perspective of management consulting that adopts a prescriptive strategy, involving standards and models for how the expert part can and ought to be worked out, and how the advisor procedure ought to be arranged and actualized. The hidden presumption is that advisors can increase the value of a customer organization and that such esteem is made through an arranged and methodical critical thinking process. Thusly this hypothesis is profoundly regulating in nature (Block, 2000; Gallessich, 1982; Griener and Metzger, 1983; Kubr, 2005; Nelson, Albon and Economy, 2009; Poulfelt, 1999; Turner, 1982).

The reasons that advisors exist from a functionalist point of view (Werr and Styhre, 2003) are that they do things customers can't (giving ability), they fill in for administrators (management substitute), have a goal viewpoint (outcasts) (Sturdy et al., 2009; O'Mahoney, 2010), give access to approaches (codification into best practice) (Baiij, Van sanctum Bosch and Vol-berda, 2005; O'Mahoney, 2010), give unique reasoning (authority in examine), approve interior choices (legitimizing) or give vital aptitudes and skill missing inside the firm (O'Mahoney, 2010).

Frostenson (2011) contends that experts who are seen as tip top consultancies – advocate that managerial consultant manage techniques and high esteem exercises. They point towards the advisor as a specialist who (a) distinguishes the issue (b) investigate and prescribe an answer and (c) execute the arrangement. This position may be defended in a practical and chronicled point of view; in any case, there has been an adjustment in the societal setting and what was before can't completely be connected today. In any case, the part of the conventional administration experts is focalizing with numerous different business zones because of their developing significance as a focused factor for have organizations (Kipping, 1999). A useful point of view that is gotten from exchange cost financial aspects and supported by specialists themselves (Hicks et al., 2009), is that experts help commodify learning and disperse it to their customers. In this point of view the expert is reliant on an examination on what the generation of the administration would cost in contrast with purchasing the asset

from outside merchants (specialists). Additionally, this information is state-of-the-art because of the way that experts work inside various customer associations (economies of scale).

The Critical Theory

The critical point of view on management consulting built up a posteriori development among researchers and different business colleges, they looked at what part the consultant embraces in social, political and social setting and how they influence the aggregate population agenda (O'Mahoney, 2010, Mohe and Seidl, 2011). When discussing the sociological capacity of the management consultant, there are as indicated by Sturdy et al., (2009) two (inverse) predominant points of view: consultants as innovators (bringing new information) or consultants as legitimizers (legitimizing existing knowledge). The critical point of view bears solid partiality to the functionalist viewpoint (Sturdy et al., 2009).

O'Mahoney (2010) clarifies that the point of view on advisors as legitimizes conspicuous difference a distinct difference to the (utilitarian) exchange cost prudent viewpoint, since it doesn't include coordinate financial advantage. Rather it includes legitimizing administrator's progressions and the specialist gives pariah data and approval to the chief's thoughts as opposed to giving mastery or acting as "specialists". Durable et al., (2009) proposes that the basic viewpoint offers a more extensive view than the practical point of view. Armbruster and Glücker, (2007) demonstrates a comparable angle contending that counseling ventures are not solely established upon financial thinking, but rather are the greater part of the circumstances fixing to hierarchical governmental issues.

Some proponents of the critical perspective on the management consultant see the consultant as the controlling party, fooling the naïve clients through rhetoric's and impression management (Werr & Styhre, 2003; Sturdy & Wright, 2011). Sturdy et al., (2009) suggests that the division into these two distinct areas (functional or critical) is far too simple as knowledge flows are far more complex and dynamic than these two perspectives suggest. Management consultants do not simply work as functionalist or criticalist, but rather as a mix of the two. However, whichever perspective adopted, the consultant works with knowledge management and can be seen as knowledge brokers: between and within their client organizations (Werr & Stjernberg, 2003) dealing with the flow, translation (Sturdy et al., 2009) and commodification of knowledge, (O'Mahoney, 2010) and as knowledge entrepreneurs (Heusinkveld, et al., 2011) to solve organizational problems.

The critical theory is adopted as the theoretical base for this study, as it best suits SMEs because the underlying assumption is that consultants can add value to a client organization and that such value is created through a planned and systematic problem-solving process (Buono & Poulfelt, 2009) not just providing outsider information as in the functionalist perspective.

MERHODOLOGY

On the premise that these research topic was time and context dependent, and the researchers believed that there are various, but equally valid perspectives of interpreting reality and the phenomenon under consideration was subject to human behaviour, the chosen philosophy of the researchers was interpretivism. The study adopted an exploratory survey research design in the course of the research. The deductive research approach was also adopted owing to the fact that the researchers were matching their assertions and findings to existing literatures and theories related to the phenomenon under discussion. Since the research was not a life project, and it was not also an action research, nor was it basically an archival research, the researchers adopted a survey strategy with a focus on SMEs in Calabar the commercial city of Cross River State Nigeria. This was essentially to keep the topic within manageable limit resulting from time constraint and financial resources.

The population of the study composed of one hundred (100) owners of SMEs in Calabar metropolis. A sample of eighty (80) SMEs owners were drawn from the region under study using the Taro Yamene formula. Being a cross sectional study, and in spite of the numerous advantages inherent in mixed methods of data collection the researchers adopted a quantitative mono method of data collection through the use of well structured close-ended questionnaire in gathering primary data for the study. In testing for the hypotheses, the Pearson Product Moment Correlation (r) technique and the Z-test statistical tool were adopted to measure the degree of association and significance between variables. Test statistics for correlation analysis is given thus;

$$r = \frac{n(\sum xy) - (\sum x)(\sum y)}{\sqrt{[n\sum x^2 - (\sum x)^2][n\sum y^2 - (\sum y)^2]}}$$

Where;

r = Coefficient of correlation

n = Number of observation

 $\sum$ = Summation

X = Independent variable

Y = Dependent variable

Decision Rule: The decision rule for correlation analysis (r) test is to reject the H_0 (Null hypothesis) if the coefficient of correlation (r) is < 1 , otherwise do not reject H_0 .**Table 2: Contingency Table for Testing Hypothesis I**

X	Y	XY	X ²	Y ²
1	232	232	1	53824
2	52	104	4	2704
$\sum X = 3$	$\sum Y = 284$	$\sum XY = 336$	$\sum X^2 = 5$	$\sum Y^2 = 56528$

Source: Researcher's Analysis, 2017.

Applying the correlation analysis formula:

$$r = \frac{n(\sum xy) - (\sum x)(\sum y)}{\sqrt{[n\sum x^2 - (\sum x)^2][n\sum y^2 - (\sum y)^2]}}$$

$$r = \frac{4(336) - (3)(284)}{\sqrt{[4(5 - (3)^2)][4(56528) - (284)^2]}}$$

$$r = \frac{1344 - 852}{\sqrt{(20 - 9)(226112 - 80656)}}$$

$$r = \frac{492}{\sqrt{(11)(145456)}}$$

$$r = \frac{492}{1264.917389}$$

$$r = \frac{492}{1264.917389}$$

$$r = 0.388958$$

$$r \cong 0.39$$

Decision: Reject the null hypothesis (H_0) if the coefficient of the correlation (r) is < 1 , otherwise do not reject H_0 . Since the coefficient of correlation (r) is less than one i.e. ($0.39 < 1$) we reject the null hypothesis and accept the alternative hypothesis which states that there is a relationship between management consultancy services and SMEs growth.

Test statistics for Z-test distribution is given thus;

$$Z = \frac{p - p_0}{\sqrt{p_0(1 - p_0)/n}}$$

Where;

P = Proportion of positive responses to the variable of interest

 P_0 = Probability of rejecting the null hypothesis i.e. 0.5

n = Total Responses

1 = Constant value

The computed value of Z is then compared with its critical value at $P \leq 0.05$ which is ± 1.96 for a 2 – tailed test.**Decision Rule:** Reject H_0 and accept H_1 if the critical value of Z is less than its computed value, and vice versa.**Hypothesis Two**

H_0 : Management consultancy services do not contribute significantly to the growth and survival of SMEs.

H_1 : Management consultancy services contribute significantly to the growth and survival of SMEs.

Responses to ascertain if management consultancy services contribute significantly to the growth and survival of SMEs

	Questions	Yes	No	Total
3.	Do you believe that management consultancy services contribute significantly to the growth and survival of SMEs?	56	16	72
4.	Does management consulting help the management of SMEs to actualize their set organizational objectives and goals?	60	13	73
	Total	116(80%)	29(20%)	145

Source: Survey Data, 2017.

Table 4.3.3: Shows that;

$$P = 116 \approx 80\%$$

$$n = 145$$

$$P_0 = 0.5$$

$$\therefore Z = \frac{0.8 - 0.5}{\sqrt{0.5(1-0.5)/145}}$$

$$Z = \frac{0.3}{\sqrt{0.25/145}}$$

$$Z = \frac{0.3}{\sqrt{0.0017}}$$

$$Z = \frac{0.3}{0.041}$$

$$Z = 7.3$$

Decision: Since the computed Z result of 7.3 is more than its critical value of 1.96 we reject H_0 and accept H_1 which states that management consultancy services contributes significantly to the growth and survival of SMEs.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

This research work discovered that there is a relationship between management consultancy services and SMEs growth and development in the region. This was demonstrated by testing the theory utilizing the correlation coefficient technique. The outcome demonstrated a positive relationship (0.39), suggesting that there is without a doubt a connection between the two variable and that they are not totally unrelated but rather associated. The outcome was in accordance with the findings of Bruhn, Karlan, and Shoar (2010) as discussed in the literature review section. Their study demonstrated the beneficial outcome of management consulting on the development of SMEs which is in line with the current study. Secondly, it was also buttressed from the result of the Z-test that there is a management consultancy services contributes significantly to the growth and sustainability of SMEs in the region. As substantiated by the Stanford Social Innovation Review (SSIR), in their resulting assessment of the program led by Bruhn, Karlan, and Shoar (2010) found out that 80% expansion in SMEs and 120% expansion in benefits for the SMEs were achieve through the assistance received from management consultants.

CONCLUSION

Conclusion and recommendations

The SMEs segment is imperative as found in the study, its progression essentially impacts on the general advancement of national economies and even social circle (through business) in numerous nations. This powers

academicians and different bodies to always investigate facilitators and deterrents of SMEs development. Various help programs have been created in different nations for diminishing/expelling hindrances for SMEs development. Frequently, they focused on money related help (credit programs) or instructive impact. These impacts together with SMEs bolster projects' exercises have been somewhat all around broke down and reported (Chrisman and McMullan, 1996). Be that as it may, numerous different impacts on SMEs advancement and development can likewise be watched. One of them is the utilization of expert business counseling administrations that bring extra skill and give a specific push to SMEs development. This happens in light of the fact that counseling incorporates enlightening, specialized, preparing and other outside impacts with attributes of individual organizations.

It is demonstrative that business people and independent companies in Nigeria utilize the administrations of expert administration specialists in a little volume. There are a few explanations behind this; the most critical is the underdevelopment of that particular sort of counseling administration, absence of consciousness of business visionaries about this kind of administration, high costs, and so on. The exploration unmistakably demonstrated that there isn't sufficient shared comprehension between the expert and the proprietor of an independent company, absence of clear advantages the administration will include and cost, however in generally speaking the proprietor administrators were ready to embrace the administrations. Having basically examined the discoveries of this work, the specialist makes the accompanying proposals; initially, proprietor administrators of SMEs ought to forcefully receive the administrations of administration experts to support their ability and maintainability. Research has uncovered that in a thick aggressive business condition, for example, Nigeria survival is the best most need of firms.

SMEs in Nigeria because of abnormal state of rivalry from bigger firms, absence of government bolster and even sufficient assets to run their operations. Thus it is essential for SMEs to plan sufficient techniques as they provide guidance to what the business has as a main priority and furthermore distinguishes courses through which they can accomplish their objectives. All these are adequately given by management consultants.

Furthermore, Nigerian government ought to finance management consultancy services for SMEs, as fund has been recognized as one of the hindering factor to them securing the managerial consulting services. Ultimately, Government and other social organizations ought to forcefully take part in the scattering and prepping of owner-managers in managerial capital.

REFERENCES

- [1] Akingbolu, R. (2014). "Why 70% of SMEs in Nigeria Fail," <http://www.thisdaylive.com/articles/why-70of-smesfailinnigeria%20experts/71911/> accessed on 23 September 2017
- [2] Appelbaum, S.H., Ritchie, S. & Shapiro, B.T. (1994). Mentoring revisited: An organisational Behaviour Construct. *The International Journal of Career Management*, Vol. 6 No. 3, pp. 3-10.
- [3] Appelbaum, S.H. & Steed, A.J. (2005). The critical success factors in the client consultant relationship. *Journal of Management Development*, Vol. 24 No. 1, pp. 68-93.
- [4] Banerjee, Abhijit, Karlan, D. & Zinman, J. (2015). "Six Randomized Evaluations of Microcredit: Introduction and Further Steps." *American Economic Journal: Applied Economics* 7 (1): 1–21.
- [5] Barisic, A. & Bozicevic, M. (2013). Role of Management Consulting in a Process of Professionalization of SME Management. *Journal of Entrepreneurial Learning*, 3 (2) p 144-159
- [6] Block, P. (2000). *Flawless Consulting*. San Francisco: Pfeiffer
- [7] Blunsdon, B.J. (2002). "Beneath fashion: Why is there a market for management consulting services?" Professional service Firms workshop, university of Alberta, Edmonton, Canada. <http://canback.com/blunsdon.pdf>, accessed 15 October 2017
- [8] Bower, M. (1982) The Forces That Launched Management Consulting Are Still at Work, *Journal of Management Consulting* No.1. pp. 4-6.
- [9] Brown, S.L. and Eisenhardt, K.M. (1997), "The art of continuous change: Linking complexity theory and time-paced evolution in relentlessly shifting organizations", *Administrative Science Quarterly*, Vol. 42, pp. 1-34.
- [10] Brown, T.L. (1990), "Match up with a Mentor", *Industry Week*, Vol. 239, pp. 18.
- [11] Bruhn, M. & David, M. (2009). "In Pursuit of Balance: Randomization in Practice in Development Field Experiments." *American Economic Journal: Applied Economics* 1 (4): 200 – 232.
- [12] Bruhn, M., Karlan, D. & Shoar, A. (2010). The Impact of Consulting Services on Small and Medium Enterprises: Evidence from a Randomized Trial in Mexico (PDF file). <https://karlan.yale.edu/papers/> (accessed 03 August 2017). [Businessdictionary.com](http://www.businessdictionary.com), accessed 15 November 2017.

- [13] de Mel, Suresh, David, M., & Woodruff, C. (2008). "Returns to Capital in Microenterprises: Evidence from a Field Experiment." *Quarterly Journal of Economics*, 123 (4), 29–72.
- [14] Deakins, D. (2000). *Entrepreneurship and Small Firms*. McGraw-Hill: London
- [15] Dyer, L. M. & Ross, C. A. (2008). Seeking Advice in a Dynamic and Complex Business Environment: Impact on the Success of Small Firms. *Journal of Development Entrepreneurship*, 13(2), 133-149.
- [16] Ewah, S. (2015). *Practical Research Methodology*. Cross River: Paffelly Printers and Publishers.
- [17] Greiner, L.E. & Metzger, R.O. (1983), *Consulting to Management*. Englewood Cliffs, NJ: Prentice-Hall
- [18] Greiner, L. E., Poulfelt, F. (2009). *Management Consulting Today and Tomorrow: Perspectives and Advice from 20 Leading World Experts*. New York: Taylor & Francis
- [19] Hannabuss, S. (1997), "Counselling approaches and the workplace", *Library Management*, Vol. 18 No. 8, pp. 373-379.
- [20] Hussey J. (Ezine Articles, 2010). 'Why small business fail'. Investadvocate.com.ng, accessed 12 August 2017.
- [21] Kakabadse, N., Louchart E. & Kakabadse, A. (2006). Consultant's Role: A Qualitative Inquiry from the Consultant's Perspective. *Journal of Management Development*, 25 (5) p 416-500
- [22] Kipping, M. (1999), American Management Consulting Companies in Western Europe, 1920 to 1990: Products, Reputation, and Relationships, *The Business History Review*, Vol. 73, No. 2, pp. 190-220.
- [23] Kipping, M. & L. Engwall, (2001). *Management Consulting: The Emergence and Dynamics of a Knowledge Industry*, Oxford University Press
- [24] Kubr, M. (1996). *Management Consulting: A Guide to the Profession*, International Labour Office (ILO), Geneva
- [25] Kubr, M. (2004). *Management Consulting: A Guide to the Profession*. (4th ed.) International Labour Office (ILO), Geneva
- [26] Lenhardt, V. (2004). *Coaching for meaning: the culture and practice of coaching and team building*, Palgrave Macmillan, Basingstoke.
- [27] McKenna, C. (2006). *The World's Newest Profession: Management Consulting in the Twentieth Century*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- [28] McKenzie, David J. (2015). "Identifying and Spurring High-Growth Entrepreneurship : Experimental Evidence from a Business Plan Competition." Policy Research Working Paper Series 73-91. The World Bank. <https://ideas.repec.org/p/wbk/wbrwps/7391.html>.
- [29] Ojasalo, J. (2001). Managing customer expectations in professional services. *Managing Service Quality*, Vol. 11 No. 3, pp. 200-212.
- [30] O'Mahoney, J. (2010). *Management Consultancy*. Oxford: Oxford University Press.
- [31] Ormerod, R.J. (1997). "The design of organisational intervention: choosing an approach", *Omega*, Vol. 25 No. 4, pp. 415-435.
- [32] Ortenblad, A. (2005). Of Course Organizations Can Learn! *The Learning Organization*, Vol 12, No 2, pp. 213-218
- [33] Osuala, E.C. (2001). *Introduction to research methodology*, Onitsha: African Feb Publishers.
- [34] Oyelaran-Oyeyakin, B. (2007). *SME: Issues, Challenges and Prospects*. (PDF file), Paper delivered at FSS 2020 International Conference.
- [35] Prokesch, S. E. (1995). Unleashing the Power of Learning. *Harvard Business Review*, Vol. 75, No. 5
- [36] Rae, D. (2005). Entrepreneurial learning: a narrative-based conceptual model, *Journal of Small Business and Enterprise Development* Vol. 12 No. 3, pp. 323-335
- [37] SMEDAN & NBS Survey Report, 2013.
- [38] Sturdy, A. (1997), "The consultancy process – an insecure business", *Journal of Management Studies*, Vol. 34 No. 3, pp. 389-413.
- [39] Sturdy, A., Clark, T., Fincham, R. and Handley, K., (2009), Re-thinking the role of management consultants as disseminators of business knowledge – knowledge flows, directions and conditions in consulting projects.
- [40] Ugwuonah, G. Onodugo, V. & Ebinne, E. (2010), *Social Science Research; Principles, methods and Application*, Enugu: El'demark Publishers.

- [41] Uchegbulam, Princess, Akinyele, Samuel, Ibadunni & Ayodotun (2015). Competitive Strategy and Performance of Selected SMEs in Nigeria. International Conference on African Development Issues (CIJ-ICA DI): Social and Economic Models for Development Track
- [42] Werr, A., Stjernberg, T., and Docherty, P. (1997), "The functions of methods of change in management consulting", *Journal of Organizational Change Management*, Vol. 10 No. 4, pp. 288-307.
- [43] Werr, A., & Styhre, A. (2003) Management Consultants – Friend or Foe? Understanding the Ambiguous Client-Consultant Relationship, *International Studies of Management & Organization*, Vol. 32, No. 4, pp. 34-66 Wikipedia.com, accessed 15 November 2017.
- [44] Zainol, F., Daud, W., Arumugam, N. & Ibrahim, N. (2015). A Feasibility Study on Business Consulting Services to Small Medium Enterprises (SMEs) by Public University in Malaysia. *International Journal of Academic Research in Accounting, Finance and Management Sciences*, Vol. 5 (2) pp. 59–65